

AMINO DERIVATIVES OF SELENIUM MONOBROMIDE. PART

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The amino derivatives of selenium monobromide have been prepared by the action of selenium monobromide on some mono- and diamines. Properties of the derivatives have been studied and structures discussed.

Tronev and Grigorovich (*Zhur. Neorg. Khim.*, 1957, 2, 2400) studied the action of anhydrous ammonia gas on selenium tetrachloride at 6-8 atmosphere pressure and obtained $\text{SeCl}_4 \cdot 4\text{NH}_3$. The other compounds studied by them were $\text{SeCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{CS}(\text{NH}_2)_2$ and $\text{SeCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{en}$.

As practically no work appears to have been done on the formation of compounds of selenium monobromide with amines, the present investigation has been undertaken to study the formation of its derivatives with aromatic primary amines in CS_2 .

EXPERIMENTAL

Selenium monobromide was prepared by the method of Lenher and Kao (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 772). The other chemicals used were of E. Merck or B.D.H. 'extra pure' quality.

General Method of Preparation.—A solution of the amine in CS_2 was slowly added to a solution of selenium monobromide in CS_2 with constant shaking till complete precipitation. The amine solution was then added in slight excess and the mixture left for about an hour. The precipitate was filtered and washed with CS_2 till the washings ceased to form any precipitate with selenium monobromide. It was dried at the room temperature in a vacuum desiccator, analysed, and its properties were studied.

Selenium was estimated as selenium metal in strong HCl solution by reducing it with SO_2 . Bromine was estimated by Piria and Schiff's method, and nitrogen by Duma's method in a Gallenkamp's electric furnace.

General Properties.—The compounds are coloured, amorphous, and fairly stable, and are practically insoluble in organic solvents. These hydrolyse very slowly in cold water and almost completely, when boiled, and decompose when treated with dilute acids or alkalis.

On heating alone, these furnish a greyish white sublimate, which is soluble in water, acidic, and responds to the tests for bromine and amino group. Derivatives with monoamines afford the sublimate at lower temperatures than those with the diamines. When heated with soda-lime, the corresponding amines separate out and condense in the cooler part of the tube. All the compounds respond to the diazo test.

DISCUSSION

The effective atomic number of selenium in these compounds is 36, which is a stable configuration and is probably responsible for the stability of the compounds.

The compounds may be represented as (I) in the case of monoamine, such as aniline, and as (II) in the case of diamine, such as benzidine.

TABLE I
Compounds of selenium monobromide with primary monoamines.

Amine.	Derivatives.	Colour.	M.P.	% Selenium.		% Bromine.		% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Aniline	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Black	144°	31.29	31.34	31.68	31.72	5.57	5.55
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Brownish black	149°	29.70	29.69	30.06	30.08	5.24	5.26
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Brown	161°	29.72	29.69	30.05	30.08	5.24	5.26
<i>o</i> -Anisidine	$(\text{Se}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{O.C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_2)\text{Br}_2$	Black	168°	28.07	28.01	28.31	28.35	4.95	4.96
<i>o</i> -Phenetidine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O.C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Greenish black	153°	26.71	26.68	26.98	27.01	4.76	4.73
<i>p</i> -Phenetidine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O.C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Pinkish grey	161°	26.70	26.68	26.97	27.01	4.71	4.73
Benzylamine	$(\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)_2)\text{Br}_2$	Greyish white	97°	29.75	29.69	30.11	30.08	5.23	5.26
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Light brown	209°	29.72	29.69	30.07	30.08	5.29	5.26
α -Naphthylamine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Ash grey	206°	26.09	26.15	26.44	26.47	4.66	4.63
β -Naphthylamine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Brownish red	198°	26.07	26.15	26.45	26.47	4.67	4.63
<i>p</i> -Anisidine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{O.C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Brownish black	146°	27.98	28.01	28.33	28.35	4.98	4.96

TABLE II
Compounds of selenium monobromide with primary diamines.

Amine.	Derivatives.	Colour.	*M.P.	% Selenium.		% Bromine.		% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Benzidine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{NH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Greyish black	211°	31.51	31.47	31.84	31.85	5.64	5.58
<i>o</i> -Tolidine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Black	213°	29.75	29.80	30.17	30.17	5.31	5.28
<i>p</i> -Phenyl- enediamine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Black	207°	38.14	37.09	37.51	37.54	6.54	6.57
Dianisidine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{O}(\text{NH}_2)\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{NH}_2\text{OCH}_3)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Brownish black	210°	28.15	28.11	28.51	28.45	5.01	4.96

* Decomposes before melting.

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